

Skills 4 eossc

D8.4 - Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan – intermediate version

Lead Partner:	GARR
Version:	1.0
Status:	Final
Dissemination Level:	PU: Public
Document Link:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14797931
DOI:	10.5281/zenodo.14797931

Deliverable Abstract

This Deliverable describes the intermediate report of the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities and the updated plan for the project Skills4EOSC.

Skills4EOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101058527 and from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040140]

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by Parties of the Skills4EOSC Project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The Skills4EOSC project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under grant n° 101058527 and by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee under grant n° 10040140.

DELIVERY SLIP

<i>Date</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Partner/Activity</i>	<i>Date</i>
<i>From:</i>	Sara Di Giorgio	GARR	25.03.2024
<i>Moderated by:</i>	Sara Di Giorgio	GARR	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Dominique Green	UEDIN	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Betty Evangelinou	GRNet	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Nana Anastasopoulou	GRNet	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Eva Méndez	U3CM	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Irakleitos Souyioultzoglou	OPERAS	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Curtis Sharma	TU Delft	25.03.2024
<i>Contributor:</i>	Gabriella Paolini	GARR	25.03.2024
<i>Reviewed by:</i>	Fulvio Galeazzi	GARR	27.03.24
<i>Approved by:</i>	Emma Lazzeri	GARR	29.03.24

DOCUMENT LOG

<i>Issue</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Comment</i>	<i>Author</i>
v.0.1	29.01.24	Draft created	Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)
V.0.2	27.03.24	Reviewed by	Fulvio Galeazzi (GARR)
v.0.3	28.03.24	Final edits	Sara Di Giorgio, Emma Lazzeri (GARR)

V.1.0	29.03.24	Version approved	Emma Lazzeri, Sara Di Giorgio (GARR)
-------	----------	------------------	---

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC	Competence Centre
CCs	Competence Centres
Comms	Communications
D&E&C	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	European Open Science Cloud Association
EUA	European University Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
Knowledge Broker	One of the actors at the Science for Policy interface, acting as impartial mediator between science and policy actors.
LERU	League of European Research Universities
MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
OS	Open Science
OSRI	Open Science Ready Institution
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
ToT	Training of Trainers

UNITE!	University Network for Innovation, Technology and Engineering
VRT	Virtual Round Table

Table of contents

Executive summary	6
1.....Introduction	7
2.....Report on dissemination and communication activities	10
2.1 Project web site.....	10
2.2 Social Media Channels.....	13
2.2.1 The Fellowship Programme campaign.....	14
2.3 Participation in third parties events.....	16
3.....Report on engagement	23
4.....Report on exploitation	34
5.....Plan for the next period	36

Executive summary

Skills4EOSC project focusses on creating a training ecosystem for Open Science and FAIR, whose ultimate outcome is to foster the development of a skilled and digitally-prepared workforce for EOSC. The project is setting up a pan-European network of competence centres and support networks in order to enable the practice of Open Science with adequate knowledge of standards, applications and tools and best practices for delivering, managing, re-using, sharing and analysing FAIR data, as well as other digital research objects to exploit the potential of the EOSC. To achieve this, a well-executed communication, dissemination, and exploitation (D&E&C) where the community of practice is partner and not only recipient alongside the whole process is necessary.

This deliverable is an update to D8.3 “Skills4EOSC Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation” [D8.3]. Since the methodology, objectives, stakeholders, campaigns, activities and KPIs largely remain the same, only the updates and changes are noted in this deliverable. Where action items appear in D8.3 but are not mentioned in D8.4, these activities remain within the plan.

This document describes the specific D&E&C activities, providing an overview of the mid-term project communication and dissemination activities and an assessment of the exploitation plan. These activities are undertaken by Work Package 8 with the support of the whole communication team of the partners.

1 Introduction

Skills4EOSC's overall objective is to provide Open Science Commons and create an EOSC-ready skilled European workforce, connecting existing centres of competence in open science and scientific data management to build a future based on Open Science and FAIR/ELSI/RRI data practices. The activities reported in this deliverable are based on the objectives, value propositions and methodology outlined in D8.3 "Skills4EOSC Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan", offering a mid-term overview of the project's outreach.

The main objectives of the D&C&E plan have been defined as follows:

1. **Engaging stakeholders through consultation and co-creation activities** to develop project outcomes inclusively and ensure success through broad consensus.
2. **Promoting project initiatives** like the fellowship program, communities of practice, and targeted training programs to encourage participation and gather feedback for further enhancement.
3. **Providing communication assistance to all project work packages** and partners to ensure successful visibility of their activities.
4. **Disseminating project results through appropriate channels** and fostering wider exploitation by establishing synergies, agreements, and collaborations with national and international actors and projects.
5. **Supporting the Skills4EOSC training platform** as a tool for the Training of Trainers (ToT) action and exploring the integration of project results, such as the FAIR by design methodology for learning materials, within the Consortium.

The following Key exploitable project outputs will be addressed with the D&E&C measures:

Standardisation	QA and skills recognition	Networks of competences	Accelerating training
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MVS for identified profiles • European curriculum for data stewards • “OS essentials” for academic courses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared framework for competence recognition • Methodology for FAIR-by-design learning materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional networks for data stewards, researchers and others • European user support network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Science4Policy” course designs and resource kits for Competence Centres • Generic and thematic ToT course designs

Table 1 Skills4EOsc KERS

The key target audiences of the project are described extensively in Section 2 of the D8.3 and summarised in Table 2

Target audiences		
1	Science professionals	This category encompasses individuals working in universities, public, and private Research-Performing Organizations (RPOs), including researchers, data stewards, managers, support staff, legal experts, and trainers.
2	Public sector	Governmental organizations, ministries, funding bodies, and agencies, which play critical roles in providing policy, funding in implementing open science (OS) and FAIR principles.
3	Academy and Research	Research and academia organisations, including public and private Research Performing Organizations (RPOs), national and international Research Infrastructures (RIs), universities, European University networks, national conferences of rectors, and international associations.

4	Industry	Professionals and companies involved in using or producing research data, particularly related to the EOSC building process. This includes industries linked to EOSC, training providers, certification agencies, Gaia-X, and initiatives for the Common European Data Spaces.
5	OS and EOSC actors	This group comprises entities directly involved in advancing EOSC, including the EOSC Association, Steering Board, initiatives, projects, Task Forces, national initiatives, structures, Mandated Organizations, and OS/FAIR Advocates like RDA, OpenAIRE, and GO FAIR Foundation.

Table 2- Skills4EOSC Target audiences

In response to the challenge of limited resources for dissemination and communication compared to the project's scope, we've leveraged consortium diversity and partner motivation. Our strategy focuses on targeted communication and engagement activities, utilising various channels and instruments to raise awareness, encourage participation, and facilitate adoption of project outputs. We prioritize engagement with science professionals, academia, and relevant stakeholders at both national and pan-European levels to maximize impact and promote OS skill development.

To ensure the maximum exploitation of project outputs, we are actively engaging with pan-European entities such as EOSC actors and OS advocates. Additionally, through networks of national competence centres, we are reaching out to national stakeholders, as well as inter-regional entities, to promote key project results. Our main target groups for this engagement are the public sector, with academia and research being secondary targets.

2 Report on dissemination and communication activities

In the first 18 months of the project, communication and dissemination activities focused on creating a digital presence for Skills4EOSC, liaising and establishing synergies with relevant EOSC-related projects and existing Open Science Competence Centres, engaging with relevant stakeholders in co-creation campaigns, communicating on project objectives and disseminating the first results.

The main communication and dissemination channels are the web site, social channels (Linkedin and X), on-line and on-site events and webinars, questionnaires on EU Survey, participation in external events, articles and publications.

2.1 Project web site

The Skills4EOSC’s website, www.skills4eosc.eu, was launched on M1 at the Kick off meeting (September 2022) and it presents the main outputs and activities of the project.

During the reporting period, the project website featured several sections. These sections included news related to project activities, event participation, and ongoing collaborations.

A total of 20 news articles were published in the first 18 months. The table below lists and links the articles according to their topics.

Type of content topic	Articles published
Project results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Skills4EOSC video for the European Year of Skills – The first Training of Trainers webinar on Science4Policy – Launch of Skills4EOSC, GARR-led Project for Open Science Training in Europe
Events, webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EOSC Winter School: Skills4EOSC Participation Report – Skills4EOSC Workshop at the 18th International Digital Curation Conference IDCC24 – Skills4EOSC at EOSC Winter School – Webinar on FAIR-by-Design Methodology: developing FAIR

	<p>materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Join Skills4EOSC at the 4th Open Science FAIR Conference in Madrid – Join us at EOSC Symposium 2023 – Skills4EOSC at ENRIO 2023 Congress on research integrity – Translating Open Science and FAIR policies into practice in Finland, 29 may 2023, Webinar – Skills4EOSC takes part in the open FDO workshop on next 30 March 2023 – Skills4EOSC at the RDA Plenary Meeting
Stakeholder consultation and engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Skills4EOSC launches second call for Fellowship Programme – Skills4EOSC Fellowship Programme call now open: join the future of Open Science! – Skills4EOSC releases 1st draft of FAIR by Design Methodology for community review – Survey on Data Stewards in Italy – Skills4EOSC releases 1st Draft of Open Science Career Profiles and MVS for community review
Collaborations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strengthening Open Science in Hungary: Skills4EOSC with KIFÜ – MoU is signed with the project NI4OS-Europe

A tracking tool monitors the number of the unique visitors on the web site.

From January 2023 to January 2024, the website www.skills4eosc.eu experienced a positive growth trend in website visits. Indeed, visits increased over the year and peaked significantly in September 2023. The following graph illustrates the website visits throughout 2023.

The website hosts the **Competence Centres Network Registry** (<https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network>) featuring profiles of six Competence Centres. The content has been agreed upon with the CCs and presents their organizational and operational activities. The registry will be continuously

updated as other Competence Centres join Skills4EOOSC and sign the MoU to enter the Network. Currently, Germany (NFDI), Holland (RNDL), Austria, Spain, and Hungary (KIFU) are in the process of joining.

Another important section of the website is dedicated to **participation and co-creation**. This section is divided into five sub-sections:

1. **Materials for community review:** The project results subjected to community review and validation are indicated. The project outcomes, all available on the project's channel on Zenodo, undergo review and improvement by stakeholders. Feedback is collected through online surveys developed using EUSurvey, a free, open-source surveying tool funded by the European Commission. It offers various question types, including free text fields and complex elements like editable tables and galleries. The technical infrastructure ensures security and data protection compliance, including anonymized processing of personal data. It supports surveys in 23 official EU languages and is available for free. We conducted consultation and co-creation activities to develop project outcomes and ensure their inclusiveness and success based on broad consensus. The co-creation campaigns conducted so far, focus on Skills4EOOSC FAIR-by-Design Learning Materials Methodology, the Skills4EOOSC MVE Survey, the Recognition Framework and a Survey on Data Stewards in Italy. We consulted researchers, experts from significant working groups, and EOOSC-related initiatives, including EOOSC-A Task Forces on Upskilling Countries, Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths, Research Careers, Recognition, and Credit, as well as the EOOSC Forum Coordinator of INFRAEOOSC, the Community of Practice of Training Coordinators, the RDA ETHRD group, and the JRC community of trainers.
2. **How to join us:** In this section, users are directed towards a series of activities for collaboration, and referred to the framework document for collaboration available on Zenodo. However, it is not mandatory to sign it to initiate collaborations.
3. **Collaborations:** here are listed the most important projects and initiatives with which Skills4EOOSC has established cooperation and shared activities.

4. **Fellowship Programme:** contains information about the two Fellowship Programme calls, designed for aspiring data professionals working in open science who wish to submit applications to participate. The first call ran from August 31st to October 31st, 2023, and selected 4 Fellows residing at 4TU.ResearchData (Netherlands), Technology University Denmark, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany), University of Edinburgh (UK). The second call was open from February 29th to March 17th, 2024. Eight applications have been submitted and decisions will be made and communicated by May 16th 2024.
5. **Learning platform:** this provides access to the Moodle platform for the ToT courses (learning.Skills4EOSC.eu).

2.2 Social Media Channels

Skills4EOSC is active on two social media channels: X (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn, aiming to reach, communicate with, and engage its audience. These channels are widely used by our partners to disseminate project information, thus enhancing the reach of our communication efforts.

The main objectives of our social media strategy include raising awareness of the project's activities and outputs, as well as expanding its reach. Communication activities are vital in supporting stakeholder engagement and fostering collaborations and synergies with other projects and initiatives. Finally, they drive traffic to the Skills4EOSC website, where interested individuals can find and review relevant project outcomes.

X (ex Twitter)

<p>Joined: September 2022</p> <p>URL: https://twitter.com/Skills4Eosc</p> <p>User name: @Skills4Eosc</p> <p>Number of followers: 710</p> <p>Number of posts, including repost: 579</p> <p>Number of original posts: 125</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the Twitter profile for Skills4Eosc. The header includes the name 'Skills4EOSC' and '579 posts'. The profile picture is a circular logo with 'Skills 4 eosc'. The bio reads: 'Skills for the European #OpenScience commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and #FAIR science'. It also shows 'Joined September 2022', '121 Following', and '687 Followers'. There are logos for 'Supporting eosc' and the European Union.</p>
---	--

LinkedIn

<p>Joined: September 2022</p> <p>URL: https://www.linkedin.com/company/skills4eosc/</p> <p>User name: @Skills4Eosc</p> <p>Number of followers: 462</p> <p>Number of original posts: 16</p>	<p>The screenshot shows the LinkedIn company page for Skills4Eosc. The header features the 'Skills 4 eosc' logo and 'Open Science Commons'. The bio states: 'Skills for the European #OpenScience commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and #FAIR science'. It lists 'Education - 413 followers - 51-200 employees' and 'Fulvio & 50 other connections follow this page'. There are buttons for '+ Follow' and 'Visit website'. A navigation bar at the bottom includes 'Home', 'About', 'Posts', 'Jobs', and 'People'.</p>
--	--

2.2.1 The Fellowship Programme campaign

As an example of the Skills4EOSC 'core comms team' tasked with coordinating and supporting communication activities, we highlight the communication campaigns of the Fellowship Programme. Two calls were

conducted, one in September-October 2023 and another in December-March 2024.

To promote the first and second Call of the Fellowship Programme, we designed a communication campaign. The aim of the campaign was to disseminate the initiative as widely as possible among the various hosting institutions. The target audience of the campaign was data professionals with a passion for Open Science, FAIR data, and research data management practices. The period of the first call was from 31st August to 31st October 2023. During this period, we posted 12 posts on social media channels LinkedIn and X, each dedicated to a single hosting institution. In addition to the text, a customized graphic was created for each hosting institution, incorporating the colors and structure of the Skills4EOSC visual identity. The second call was from 21st December 2023 to 29th February 2024. Again, 10 posts were designed and published on social platforms, each with a customized graphic according to the respective hosting institution. Thanks to these two social media campaigns, it was possible to spread the opportunity among various hosting institutions and their respective communication channels, and Skills4EOSC has strengthened its visual identity and increased visits to the channels and reactions to the published posts. For example, data from the first mentioned campaign show that during the post

publication period, more than 220 reactions to the posts and more than 50 shares of the same were obtained.

2.3 Participation in third parties events

Skills4EOSC partners actively participate in relevant third party events as speakers, organising sessions or workshops, presenting posters or giving talks. A non-exhaustive list of the events held to date, is provided below.

Event title	Typology	Date	Target	Venue	Added value for Skills4EOSC
RDA 20th Plenary	On site	March 21-23 2023	Researchers, data scientists, policymakers, and data stewards	Gothenburg, Sweden	Project presentation, collection of user needs, alignment and collaboration with RDA Tiger activities.
KU Leuven Open Science Day	National on site event	2 May 2023	Researchers and general public	Leuven	Presenting the project seeking synergies and collaboration. See at https://zenodo.org/records/8425367
User Rights Network Symposium	Hybrid International	17 May 2023	Legal researchers	American University Washington College of Law	To share information on funded projects that may address Copyright Limitations and Exceptions See at https://zenodo.org/record/8425719
EOSC National tripartite in Italy	Hybrid/on site	5 June 2023	Ministries, RPOs, Funders the wider EOSC research community	Italian National Research Council in Rome	Presenting the project outside its region of influence, seeking synergies and collaboration with other countries/regions. See the slide
Meeting of the Community of Practice for Training Coordinators	National/International event	13-June 2023	Training coordinators within RDM and OS	Online	Presented the overall project and deliverable 6.1 "Mapping of existing Open Science networks". Received valuable input on the work done and feedback on how to improve it, e.g. by including Citizen See at https://zenodo.org/records/8344074
EOSC France tripartite event	On site event	13-14 June 2023	Researchers, data scientists, policymakers, and data stewards	Montpellier, France	Presenting the project to the French Open science research community with some additional informations about TF Data Stewardship Curricula & Career Paths and showing the links with initiatives in France. See at https://eoscfrence2023.sciencesconf.org/477438

Event title	Typology	Date	Target	Venue	Added value for Skills4EOSC
National RDM Network summer meeting	On site event	27 June 2023	RDM professionals at Danish universities (libraries)	Copenhagen, Denmark	Presentations of selected outputs of relevance for the national network; Starter kit, Skills4EOSC fellowship. Discussion of the possibility of having a Danish CC. Discussion of uptake of S4E outputs by the natl. network. see https://forskningsdata.dk/rdmnetvaerk/about-the-danish-rdm-network/
IP Researchers Europe Conference (IPRE)	International event on site	29-30 June	legal researchers	WIPO and WTO, Geneva, Switzerland	The presentation will address some issues concerning automated uses (text and data mining) of copyrighted works for research purposes, which is central to our project.
Danish EOSC Coordination Forum	National/local event. Hybrid	22-August 2023	Researchers, RPO, data stewards, librarians, Ministry of Higher Education and Science, DeIC	Online	The presentation gives an overview of the Skills4EOSC project, the Danish consortium participating in the project, and Skills4EOSC key concepts. See at https://zenodo.org/records/8340729
DiPP 2023	On site	07-10 Sept 2023	OS community in Bulgaria, policy makers,	Burgas, Bulgaria	Presenting the project and establishing collaborations with local and national initiatives. See at https://dipp2023.math.bas.bg/programme
ENRIO 2023 Congress on Research Integrity Practice	Hybrid, On site	12 - 14 September 2023	Experts, researchers, policymakers in the field of research integrity.	Paris, France	Project presentation 'Creating a Collaborative Training Ecosystem for Responsible Open Science' for establishing collaborations.
CoRDI2023 (conference on Research Data Infrastructure)	On site	12 - 14 September 2023	RIs; German NFDI 750 attendees - 10% from outside Germany	Karlsruhe, Germany	Poster https://zenodo.org/records/8349136

Event title	Typology	Date	Target	Venue	Added value for Skills4EOSC
EOSC Symposium 2023	On site, Hybrid	20-22 September 2023	participants across EOSC projects, ministries, policy makers, Universities and RPOs, RIs		Presentation/publicising of Skills4EOSC Fellowship programme; Organiser of the session: ' Skills & Training: European alignment on skills and training: Charting the path forward '
Open Science Fair	On site	26 September	Open Science communities, universities	Madrid Spain	Presenting the project outcomes: See at https://zenodo.org/record/8425514
Trieste Next (Trieste science festival)	On site	23 September 2023	Researchers, students, general public	Trieste, Piazza Unità d'Italia	Introduce Open Science and the profession of the data steward to citizens, disseminate Skills4EOSC mission. See the presentation here
10th Portuguese RDM Forum	On site	14-15 November 2023	Researchers, Data professionals in research	Setubal, Portugal	Linked to T6.3.1 Harmonisation and Creation of Professional Networks - Data Stewards Networks. This is an opportunity to publicly support the nascent moves in Portugal to establish a national DS network
Data Management and Open Science Workshop at INGV	Italian national on site event	15 November 2023	Researchers, research support staff, research data managers, data stewards, policy/decision makers	Rome, Italy	focusing on data sharing's impact on policy and decision making
Professionalisation of RDM experts WG meeting	Online national/local event (external)	20 November 2023	WG members, mainly research support personnel from Finnish universities		Disseminate information about the project and ongoing developments
NIFDI4DS Hackathon	On site	21-22 November 2023	Researchers, Data and Software professionals, RDA co-chairs	Deutsche Zentralbibliothek Medizin, Cologne,	The event is linked to T6.3.3a "FAIR Data for AI" and sponsored by NFDI, it's facilitated in collaboration with the FAIR4ML RDA IG. This event offered valuable insights to ensure a high-quality

Event title	Typology	Date	Target	Venue	Added value for Skills4EOSC
				Germany	outcome for T6.3.3a. see https://zenodo.org/record/8425436
10ans de Dialogu'ist	On site national/local event	30 November 2023	Research support staff from french scientific organization	Marseille, France	Demonstrate the possible links between the French structure "Recherche Data Gouv" ecosystem and the outcomes of the project see https://indico.mathrice.fr/event/383/timetable/
AI4EOSC Platform: User's workshop	Hybrid international event	15-16 November 2023	AI4EOSC, Imagine-AI proj communities;	KIT SAS Institute of Informatics	Dissemination of Skills4EOSC project, specifically the concept of S4E Competence Centre. see https://zenodo.org/records/8093818
HPC Forum	National event (local) on site	11/16/2023	HPC, HPDA, IA, and EOSC users	Sofia Tech Park, Bulgaria	Presenting the project seeking synergies and collaboration. See https://events.iict.bas.bg/event/72/timetable/#20231116
#digiRoundtable V	hybrid (online, in person in Vienna)	22 November 2023		Museumsbund Österreich (Austrian Museums Association)	Dissemination of Skills4EOSC, potential collaboration and discussion with participants. See recording https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fS--B_7ChFA
FAIR-by-Design Methodology: how to develop FAIR materials	On line	04 December 2023	learning materials developers		Dissemination of the FAIR-by-Design methodology see presentation https://zenodo.org/records/10256852
EPOS Data Portal Training	Online international event	1/25/2024	Research in solid Earth science, open data		Project presentation within the training on a tool (portal) enabling open science and demonstrating usefulness of sharing scientific data.

Event title	Typology	Date	Target	Venue	Added value for Skills4EOSC
Seminar "Responsible Practice in Open Science"	Hybrid national/local event	1/29/2024	Researchers	University of Latvia	Dissemination of Skills4EOSC project and potential collaborations on Ethics
EOSC Winter School 2024	On site event	29 January - 1 February 2024	Members of HE projects	Thessaloniki Greece	Skills4EOSC team actively organised and participated in the Opportunity Area 5 Skills, training, rewards, recognition and upscaling session
'FAIR for prosthetics design and assessment' BoF (RDA's 22nd Plenary Meeting)	On line international	13 February 2024	Thematic community		The workshop, held under Task 6.3.3b (FAIR data for Health & Technology), aims to promote FAIR practices in the sector. Additionally, there is potential for establishing an Interest Group within RDA focused on this area. See https://www.rd-alliance.org/fair-prosthetics-design-and-assessment
FAIR-by-Design workshop @ IDCC'24	Hybrid International event	19 February 2024	Researchers, software developers, learning materials developers	Surgeons Quarter, Edinburgh, UK	Training on the FAIR-by-Design methodology, showcase its applicability to other digital objects such as software object see https://fair-by-design-methodology.github.io/IDCC24workshop/latest/
YUFERING project. final project meeting	Online international event	21 February 2024	Members of YUFE EUA + AB and Eu Research Agency representative		Skills4EOSC was mentioned as the game-changer in the continuity of the YUFE Open Science syllabus
AURORA network WP meeting	On line international event	8 March 2024	thematic community; participants in AURORA WP6 Open Science, invited talks on the Minimum Viable Skillsets		Potential adoption of MVS to provide a shared framework for training activities.

3 Report on engagement

In line with the methodology and objectives outlined in D8.3 “Skills4EOSC Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation”, each work package conducted tailored engagement initiatives to identify stakeholder needs and co-create and validate project outcomes. Below is an update on the key activities carried out and the results achieved.

Virtual Round Tables organised within WP1 ‘Project management’

The VRT is an activity/space developed to raise awareness and strategic alignment with the project partners. This is an activity that goes beyond the usual project activities. It acts as a guided discussion; thus, the aim is to seek for alignment, but also to identify and address potential gaps in existing work flows and to enhance common understanding. Furthermore, the VRT opened space to initiate the adoption of corrective measures whenever there was a demand or a need, such as the adoption of a central concept in order to generate conceptual alignment between the WPs or foster knowledge transfer inside of the consortium. The VRTs has proven to be a suitable instrument for carrying out these tasks. With these VRTs the project is : a) Enhancing Cohesion; b) Catering for Alignment of knowledge and experience; c) Providing Bottom-up processing and feedback; d) Stimulating Community building; e) Fostering the extended competencies of the consortium beyond project objectives; f) Addressing transversal activities beyond project objectives.

The organisation of VRT is based on the selection of a central theme and of sub-topics, defined together with the Coordinator of the project, to serve as a point of reference and for better involvement of the participants. The event has a duration of 90 minutes, the first 35 minutes are dedicated to the presentation of the agenda, theme and sub-themes, followed by a brief presentation (by the organiser or guest) on the chosen theme. The remaining time is dedicated to the guided discussion, where the participants are

encouraged to participate by the moderator and the discussion topic is not restricted to the topic that was presented.

During the reporting period, we successfully organized three VRTs, with the participation of at least one representative from each consortium member, along with the active involvement of all task leaders and members.

VRTs	Focus	Key Takeaway message
<p>1st VRT: Sustainable development and community building among the partners of the Skills4EOSC project <i>(31st March 2023)</i></p>	<p>The aim was to raise awareness and sensitize the partners that the project leads to a process: <i>Start thinking about it from the end.</i> And also, on reflecting on what actions are possible to take now in order to be successful after the project.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A summarised introduction to the concept of Skills4EOSC Competence Centre's nodes (CCs) and Competence Center's Network (CCnet) <i>(Emma Lazzeri, GARR)</i> • A short presentation "Project-oriented thinking to process-oriented thinking" <i>(Paolo Budroni, TUW)</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Broaden the Open Science concept. 2. Adapt Competence Centres (CCs) to regional contexts. 3. Tailor training materials to target groups. 4. Emphasize sustainability and community involvement.
<p>2nd VRT: Definitions of Open Science in relation to Skills4EOSC <i>(12th June 2023)</i></p>	<p>The aim was to provide strategic alignment in the chosen definition of Open Science with the project partners.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competence Centres according to the vision of the Project <i>(Emma Lazzeri, GARR)</i> • Open Science: the need for curricula <i>(Eva Méndez, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)</i> • About Open Science <i>(Kevin Ashley, DCC)</i> 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open Science varies by discipline. 2. Three core elements: knowledge access, reproducibility, and infrastructure. 3. Context-sensitive Open Science definitions work best. 4. Focus on practical actions, not rigid definitions. 5. Policies are essential for unifying diverse definitions. 6. UNESCO's comprehensive definition is

		suggested.
<p>3rd VRT:</p> <p>How the new EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2025-27 is impacting on Skill4EOSC (12th January 2024)</p>	<p>The aim was to provide strategic alignment with the project partners about specific objectives of the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) related to skills and training and specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to understand how the new EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2025-27 is impacting on Skill4EOSC • to promote the conceptual and strategic alignment of the needs of Skills4EOSC, which emerged after its first year, with version 1.2 of the SRIA. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MAR clarifies the role of aligned European curricula in promoting Open Science. 2. It emphasizes the importance of establishing proper career paths for research support professionals. 3. It encourages the use of Competence Centres to support the implementation of Open Science practices. 4. The importance of FAIR-by-design principles for ensuring the long-term usability of digital objects.

Engaging activities related to OS career profiles, skillsets and material

WP2 has engaged in activities in relation to its key outputs. The FAIR-by-design methodology has had extensive engagement within and outside of the project. Within the project, Task 2.3 led an extensive 3-day train of trainers course on the FAIR-by-design methodology. This course provided insights, tips, and recommendations for the implementation of planned training materials.. Outside of the project, the FAIR-by-design methodology has been presented at a FAIR-IMPACT FAIR Implementation Workshop, an EOSC FUTURE training in the Western Balkans, and a workshop at the International Digital Curation Conference. These interactive events were well attended and allowed the task lead to obtain relevant feedback on the FAIR-by-design methodology. Additionally, along with Task 2.1, the PATTERN project, and the EOSC Association’s Data Stewardship Curricula and Career

Paths Task Force, Task 2.3 led a workshop at OSFAIR 2023. The workshop aimed to promote new approaches to address competence gaps in Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation, clarify the role profiles and career paths of data professionals, and help design high quality FAIR learning resources for learners and educators.

The 2.1 task lead was invited by the AURORA Research & Innovation project to present the MVS profiles to their WP on Open Science. As a result of the presentation, the AURORA project is considering using the MVS as a part of their Open Science trainings.

Task 2.5 has designed the Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework. Throughout the development of the framework, this task has engaged multiple times with teams from Europass to discuss the European Digital Credentials in order to investigate its feasibility for Skills4EOSC. Additionally, Task 2.5 leader presented the current version of the Recognition Framework to OpenAIRE's Community of Practice Open Science Trainers Group. As a result, a joint task force on digital credentials was created and is now operational, with partners within and outside of Skills4EOSC.

In addition to direct engagement within and outside of the project, WP2 has launched several co-creation activities. Via the use of EU surveys, we seek continued feedback and opportunities for co-creation within Skills4EOSC partners and outside the project. The following outputs were developed and enriched through co-creation activities:

- the [MVS](#) to establish which roles are considered 'key' and drafted a first example MVS for policy makers, for internal and external consultation (March 2023). Additionally, various MVS profiles were co-created with other Skills4EOSC partners and relevant external communities. For instance, the MVS profile for Data Stewards was co-created by Data Stewards at TU-Delft and the Data Stewards Interest Group.
- the first [Draft Methodology for FAIR-by-Design Learning Material](#) for the continuous improvement of the methodology

- the [Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework](#) to collect feedback on our proposed approach to rewarding and documenting Open Science skills.

Engaging with policy makers and honest brokers

The engaging activities in WP3 include a variety of different types of activities, such as participation in relevant events, feedback and co-creation activities, as well as organisation of events for the community. Some of them have already been performed and some are foreseen for the near future.

One of the goals in WP3 is to open our work and present it in relevant events, to support and collaborate with interested stakeholders. To this end, and with the aim of testing it, the material prepared in the different development phases in WP3 was communicated in such events, some of which are depicted below.

In June 2023 the efficiency of key messages for policy makers identified in WP3 was tested in the drafting of preparatory documents for some of the policy makers that were participating to the EOSC tripartite event in Italy. The feedback was positive as messages helped in setting the scene and understanding the importance of Open Science at the level of Organisations in Research, by communicating in a direct and concise way with the target audience.

In September 2023, an unconference session was organised jointly with [DECIDO](#) project, which aims to demonstrate the transformative impact of adopting innovative methodologies, tools, and data for developing evidence-based policies by public authorities. The session "Why are Public Authorities not (yet) a relevant user group for EOSC, and what can we do to foster this?" revealed a deep interest in understanding how researchers can effectively impact on policymaking process and how can open science affect this process. Also in this case, preliminary work done by WP3 was presented and was very well received by the audience of the EOSC Symposium session, which included mainly researchers working in the field of Open Science as well as honest brokers and civil servants.

Key messages drafted by WP3 were also adopted in formal and informal meetings with policy makers and stakeholders and in science for policy interface scenarios. Various Skills4EOSC participants are involved as experts in national or institutional working groups aimed at informing policymakers (RPO governance and ministries). This engagement has facilitated the refinement of messages, making them more suitable and actionable.

In order to understand the needs of the relevant community in training, WP3 has identified a number of feedback and co-creation activities, that are performed mainly during the material preparation period. Among the regular activities of this task is the organization of community workshops, where people from the consortium, members of organisations relevant to the profiles studied in this WP, but also outside the consortium when necessary, discuss on the needs and challenges of policy makers, civil servants and honest brokers, related to the gaps in skills and knowledge in their organisations.

Furthermore, we have identified and reached out to experts in Open Science and policy-making to conduct an initial review and provide feedback (via written feedback, discussions, or interviews) on the Training Curriculum and the proposed Training of Trainers (ToTs) courses, which have been organized. In pursuit of this, pilot ToT workshops will be conducted early on to gather feedback on the content and activities slated for the final courses. Additionally, feedback workshops involving pertinent stakeholders in policymaking will be held to deliberate on the framework of the national pilot trainings, scheduled subsequent to the ToT courses.

For feedback and co-creation activities, close connection has been established also with the JRC community. Besides the discussion and feedback on the training material that is developed in WP3, the JRC community will provide us feedback on the Science4Policy Kit that is being developed in WP3, which will include best practices for Competence Centers, to be used as resources to build “Science4Policy” activities and courses.

Finally, deliverable [D3.3](#) “Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers” was developed using insights of policy makers and honest brokers, interviewed for this specific document. For the purposes of this deliverable, a feedback workshop was performed at INGV with top-level Directors and open to all profiles working at INGV from all branches and Departments, to retrieve inside information on the activity of the Honest Broker. This deliverable, as all the deliverables in WP3, was uploaded to Zenodo.

One of the main activities of WP3 is the organisation of events for the Community. These events include training courses but also informative events.

The main outcome of WP3 is to organise ToT courses for trainers on Open Science and policy making/public administration. At time of writing, 4 Train the Trainers courses are expected to be held during 2024, with different thematic areas, related to policy, for the three professional profiles (policy makers, civil servants and honest brokers) targeted in WP3. After the ToT courses, national pilot trainings will be performed from the trained trainers to end user organisations, using the material provided in the ToT courses.

Engagement activities related to Open Science ready Institutions

WP4 has devised various engagement activities. Within the framework of Skills4EOSC WP4, one of the most challenging tasks is delineating the criteria for an Open Science ready institution (OSRI) and pinpointing such institutions. To address this challenge, we introduced this topic at the event focused on SWAFS (Science With and for Society) projects conducted by EU university alliances, held in Brussels on November 30 and December 1, 2023. European University Alliances are inherently expected to embody "Open Science Universities," as demonstrated by their involvement and performance in SWAFS projects, thus meeting the qualifications for an OSRI.

In another perspective, WP4 has started planning its training in Open Science to Doctoral candidates, undergraduate students and data stewards. These first training groups might be considered the main seed for the Open Science Communities in the OS ready institutions, at least in our partner institutions.

So the training is a core content of the project, but also a chance to build up community.

Engagement activities related to Research Infrastructures and thematic communities

In May 2023, WP5 organised a workshop with the aim of discussing with the consortium partners and invited stakeholders the objectives and the themes of its foreseen training pilots. The discussion focused mainly on the challenges of discipline-specific trainings for the thematic communities in the Social Sciences and Humanities (T5.2), Solid Earth Sciences (T5.3), and Climate Change (T5.4). Participants reflected on the main elements of the research landscape in these particular fields, with particular reference to Open Science (OS) and Research Data Management (RDM) workflows. Attention was also placed to the position of Research infrastructures within the research ecosystem and their role in coordinating training activities. The workshop provided the opportunity to engage in discussions with representatives of the thematic communities and scholarly communication professionals, thus setting up the foundations for a long-term engagement process that could span beyond the project’s time frame.

Additionally, in February 2024, the above-mentioned tasks successfully reached the milestones related to delivering training pilots to the relevant thematic communities. Upon agreement to implement a combined methodological approach, the pilot sessions were delivered in different formats. Specifically, T5.3 *OS and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences* organised an open session that comprised two modules: an introductory presentation on the fundamentals of Open Science, and a training session on the digital workflows supported by the EPOS portal. The pilot was advertised on social media platforms and attracted a total number of 150 participants, on average. T5.4 *OS and RDM in Climate Change* targeted early career researchers, and organised a pilot for affiliates of the University of Trento, TU-Delft, and the Euro-Mediterranean Centre for Climate Change. The

training, which focused on a range of competences identified in the Minimum Viable Skillset for Researchers, was attended by 19 participants in total. T5.2 *OS and RDM in Social Sciences and Humanities*, delivered its pilots as a series of subsequent sessions corresponding to the main stages of the research life cycle (planning, active research and dissemination). The organisers invited participants with diverse background (researchers, librarians and Research Infrastructure/Scholarly Communication professionals), in order to assess the relevance of the pilot to a wider range of stakeholders. The 22 attendees were actively engaged in the training activities and expressed their interest in contributing to the further development and dissemination of the training materials.

Data Steward Networks and Open Science Communities

WP6 through T6.3.1 has been collaborating with several institutes and initiatives in establishing new RDM/Data Steward Networks. These currently include institutions in Ireland, Italy, the Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden) and Portugal. Through the “harmonising networks” aspect of T6.3.1, Skills4EOSC is collaborating with institutions in the US and Canada in addition to those mentioned before, and it is expected that new global collaborators will be involved before project closure. Through task 6.3.3 Skills4EOSC is collaborating with the FAIR4ML RDA Interest Group, as it aims to evaluate and recommend best FAIR practices for AI research. Finally, a Birds of Feather Session has been accepted for RDA Plenary 22 in May 2024, to establish a network for those interested in FAIR data for Health Technology research. Through T6.3.2, nine new Open Science Communities have been established across Europe. The second iteration of the incubation programme is now complete with nine out of ten course candidates completing the programme, with the expectation that another nine new OSCs will be established.

The Fellowship Programme

The first call of the Fellowship Programme ran from August 31st to October 31st, 2023, and selected 4 Fellows residing at 4TU.ResearchData

(Netherlands), Technology University Denmark, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany), University of Edinburgh (UK). The second call was open from February 29th to March 17th, 2024. Eight applications have been submitted and decisions will be made and communicated by 30 April 2024

Engaging activities with Competence Centres and user support networks

WP7 engaged with several Competence Centres to discuss the characteristics of the services offered and the needs of the respective communities. Two internal consortium workshops were organized on July 5th, 2023, and January 18th, 2024, aimed at initiating collaboration between national, regional, or thematic Competence Centres in consortium countries and Skills4EOSC for the integration of project outcomes.

Each three-hour workshop saw the participation of approximately 50 attendees. The agendas featured presentations from the Competence Centres nodes of the S4E Network, followed by interactive Q&A sessions and moderated discussions.

The feedback collected from these sessions was about services offered, organizational models, and challenges. The resulting discussion underscored crucial aspects of Competence Centres. Stakeholders' diverse needs, particularly those of researchers, were identified as central to the Competence Centres' focus. Key competence areas highlighted included FAIR principles, Open Science, Research Data Management (RDM), and Open Source Software.

The envisioned organizational models for Competence Centres encompass government-funded, collaborative network-based, and thematic structures. Collaboration and knowledge-sharing through coordination forums were emphasized to facilitate effective interaction among Competence Centres.

The Skills4EOSC Coordination Network is perceived as playing an international coordination role, developing resources, and supporting sustainability, quality assurance, and the establishment of new Competence Centres.

D 8.4 – Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan – Intermediate version

Specific meetings were also arranged with certain Competence Centres, whose affiliated organizations are not part of the project consortium, such as the French, German, and Hungarian Competence Centres, to discuss in detail the terms of collaboration and onboarding into the Skills4EOSC registry.

The WP7 also committed to identifying and contacting the User Support Networks (USNs), which are groups of individuals that provide direct support and technical and non-technical assistance to users of a particular service or resource related to OS practices. These USNs will be aligned with the different nodes of the Skills4EOSC CCs Network. In March 2024, efforts were made to organize a consultation to broaden participation through an [EU Survey](#).

4 Report on exploitation

The liaison with other EOSC-relevant projects and initiatives has been recognized since the beginning of the project as an importation set of actions, which has been documented in the internal report (sensitive) in the context of MS8.2 - Report on cooperation with related EOSC-projects and the EOSC Partnership - initial. The aim of that report was to identify projects, with which Skills4EOSC share equal emphasis on training and engagement, the adoption of FAIR principles and digital skills, and the discoverability and interoperability of targeted training and skills materials. In order to achieve better monitoring and openness of the synergies among projects, a matrix has been created to record common actions, trainings, mutually signed documents etc. In addition, in the official project website, a specific section has been created where formalized activities are broadly disseminated: <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/participate/collaborations>.

In more details over the last year, a strong collaboration channel has been developed with the project FAIR-IMPACT, with which a living document of collaboration plan has been formulated, as well as a mutual event on December 2023; namely "[FAIR-by-Design Methodology: how to develop FAIR materials](#)". Additionally, Skills4EOSC project has signed a [Collaboration agreement with KIFÜ](#) (Hungarian Governmental Information Technology Development Agency) with the aim to enhance Open Science initiatives and explore establishing an Open Science Competence Centre in Hungary. Also, during the [EOSC Winter School 2024](#), there have been extended communication activities with EuroScienceGateway. In the context of this project a training platform has been developed from which Skills4EOSC could share very constructive knowledge about setting up trainings and how can be turned into self paced trainings.

The Winter School marked a pivotal moment for starting a collaboration with the [OSCARS project](#) (Open Science Clusters Action for Research & Society), launched on January 1, 2024 and kicked off on 15 March. OSCARS' primary objective is to bring together prominent European Research Infrastructures

(RIs) to advance Open Science initiatives across Europe. To achieve this, OSCARS plans to establish thematic Competence Centres, which will serve as hubs for consolidating achievements into sustainable interdisciplinary services and practices. These efforts are aimed at empowering domain-based research and user communities while encouraging scientist engagement within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Despite being in its early stages, OSCARS has expressed keen interest in the outcomes delivered by Skills4EOSC, particularly in the [Competence Centre Charter](#), which outlines the objectives and services of the Skills4EOSC Competence Centres, and the FAIR-by-Design methodology for developing FAIR training resources. OSCARS will actively participate in upcoming Skills4EOSC events, including the public launch of the Competence Centre network on June 25th and the in-person workshop of the Competence Centres on the morning of October 21st, co-located with the EOSC Symposium 2024 in Berlin. Furthermore, OSCARS has contributed to the proposal for the unconference at the EOSC Symposium.

The FAIR-by-Design Methodology has also garnered interest from other projects and initiatives, such as [EOSC4Cancer](#) and [CLARIN](#).

An important exploitation achievement, expected to gain significant traction in the project's second half, is the adoption of Skills4EOSC outcomes by Competence Centres for Open Science that are external to the consortium. Particularly noteworthy for this reporting period is the [French Competence Centre](#), managed by the French Ministry for Research, which has committed to adopting the FAIR-by-Design methodology.

5 Plan for the next period

The engagement and exploitation activities will intensify in the upcoming period with the launch of the Competence Centres' training of trainers courses and the continuation of the co-creation and validation process of the provided resources. In particular:

Plan related to WP2 Task 2.5 (Skills4EOSC Recognition Framework) has launched a Joint Task Force on Digital Credentials. This group will be active starting April 2024. The members of the task force include Skills4EOSC partners and those outside and should enable the project to develop a widely recognized and agreed up certification/recognition framework for trainers.

Task 2.3 will organise additional engagement outside and within the project. The task will work again with FAIR-IMPACT. Tasks 2.1 and 2.3 have been collaborating to ensure that all WP2 outputs align with the FAIR-by-design methodology. Subsequently, the MVS profiles are also FAIR-by-design. Working with FAIR-IMPACT, Task 2.3 will impact FAIR signposting for the MVS profiles. Signposting is an approach used to increase the FAIRness of scholarly objects.

Plan related to WP3 In the next future the “Brainstorming Workshop on Open Science, Research Data Management and Decision-Making” that will be held online and will take place on 9th April 2024, as well as a bigger one that is still under discussion, that will take place in person and is planned for June 2024, where relevant material from the deliverable will be presented. The feedback from these two new workshops will be used to validate and update, if necessary, the information included in the [D3.3](#) “Guidelines and Best Practices for Honest Brokers”. In the next months WP3 will organise the workshop “The Practice of Informing Policy Through Evidence” dedicated to train researchers on how to communicate science and interact with policy makers and how the uptake of research outputs by policy makers and public administration can be encouraged by researchers adhering to OS practices.

Moreover, regarding Museums Open Collections and how they promote Policy Goals, a Round Table for Parliamentarians and policy administration in Brussels is also planned for the end of 2024.

Finally, the organisation of informative events is also under discussion for the next period.

Plan related to WP4 In the next period, WP4 will launch a cross-tasks survey to gather information about what the targeted users and researchers levels do they need/want to know about Open Science. This survey will also be a opportunity for engagement with Skills4EOSC. The survey results will be anonymous but one of the designed questions will explore the likelihood of the surveyed people of getting involved with the institutional OS Community that will help to create and come along with the creation of Competence Centres for training and development of Open Science skills.

We will also intensify our relationship with the already existing projects in the EOSC ecosystem (like FAIR-IMPACT) or the recent player in the scenario (e.g. OSCARS) that will help us on targeting our community and stakeholders better, as well as engage in our training activities, resources and planning, more key-actors in the EOSC ecosystem.

Plan related to WP5. T5.1 *OS and RDM skills for Research Infrastructure professionals* and T5.5 *OS and RDM skills for Open Scientific Collections* are expected to deliver their pilots in M24 (August) and M28 (December), respectively. Both tasks are preparing the training sessions in collaboration with external stakeholders and/or initiatives. More specifically, T5.1 works closely with the RITRAINplus project (coordinated by the TL), whereas T5.5 will invite museum curators to a co-design workshop, with an aim to identify the main challenges and workflows related to FAIR practices in this particular field.

T5.2 will organise a follow-up session with the participation of representatives from other Research Infrastructures, to explore ways in which the Skills4EOSC modules can be integrated into existing training resources. Accordingly, tasks T5.3 and T5.4 are currently evaluating

participant feedback, and will disseminate the training materials in the respective thematic communities.

The project will be presented at the [OPERAS 2024](#) conference.

Plan related to WP6 “Data Steward Networks”. During coming year, WP6 will continue to work with those DS network initiatives mentioned in 1.3, namely the Italian, Irish, Portuguese and Nordic Countries networks. We will continue to develop playbooks for these networks, which provide information and guidelines on the purpose and operation of the networks, ensuring a steering committee is in place, creating and implementing a roadmap for development and building and sustaining membership. We also hope that two new DS network initiatives will take off. These are a Norwegian network and a Balkan Countries network. All of these initiatives are (will be) at different stages of development, and we are transferring ideas across them as needed and appropriate. We expect during this year to also bring network initiatives into contact with their respective national Competence Centres. All steering committee members will be invited to join the RDA Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group (IG) Task Group (TG) “Networking and Knowledge Exchange” to be announced at the RDA Plenary in May 2024. This will bring further support and collaboration globally. The TG itself is currently being developed and we expect to have a full steering committee and playbook by summer, after which we will also invite established DS networks to join. We have registered a request for assistance from RDA TIGER to develop the TG into an independent IG, as there are constraints on what is possible as a TG within an established IG.

With respect to Open Science Communities (see 1.3), we expect to see the establishment of nine new groups. Challenges remain with respect to sustainability (in the local context) for some of the newly established OSCs, but the T6.3.2 task leaders are continuing to support all groups through the international network of OSCs, [INOSC](#). The next round of the incubation programme will begin in September 2024. It is expected that this round will include representatives from outside Europe as well. As we have already met

the KPIs for new networks and communities in Europe, we welcome this wider participation.

WP6 through T6.3.3, will be further engaging with the AI and Health Technology research communities through surveys, focus groups and writing sprints. We expect to complete input from members of these communities by the end of 2024 towards our evaluation and recommendation of FAIR practices in these areas. We will work with these experts through their institutions as well as relevant RDA Interest Groups.

Fellowship Programme: At present the fellowship programme secretariat is following up on applications in the second round (closed 17/03/2024) to ensure applications are complete and supporting documents are in order. Beginning of April 2024, applications will be passed to the evaluator panel and outcomes will be communicated to the eight candidates by the end of same month. Three successful fellows from the first round are yet to begin their placements, but are expected to do so during 2024 (see 1.4 above). End of fellowship surveys will be created during April 2024 via EU Survey for both fellows and host institutions, as we expect the first (call 1) fellowship to be completed at the end of April. The results of these surveys which seek to capture thoughts on the experience will be analysed, synthesised and included in the T6.4 deliverable.

Plan related to WP7 To strengthen the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre Network, a third internal consortium workshop is due to take place in April, ahead of the public launch scheduled for June 25th, 2024. Additionally, the project is actively engaged in collaboration with EOSC-related projects funded by the Horizon Europe programme within the EOSC Forum and the Opportunity Areas 05 Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling formed in the EOSC Winter School. Through this collaboration, a workshop on Competence Centres is being planned for October 21st, 2024, co-located with the next [EOSC Symposium 2024](#) in Berlin. Furthermore, a submission has been made for an Unconference, aiming to propose an entire session of the symposium dedicated to training and the centrality of Competence Centres. To ensure a constant channel of information and dissemination, the

creation of a mailing list for Competence Centres is planned, along with a series of regular appointments to facilitate exchange and collaboration on common interest topics.

Plan related to WP8 Synergies activities during the reported time period have been materialized according to initial plans and at the same time adapting to the project’s need and evolvement of EOSC environment.

Future plans for the coming months is to further expand and materialize the initialized collaboration actions and to start new ones with projects, which were not included in the *MS8.2 - Report on cooperation with related EOSC-projects and the EOSC Partnership* but have been identified as interesting initiatives, with which common goals can be shared. For example, the [OSCARS](#) project, which started on January 2024 and will contribute to the development and implementation of CCs in Europe and [EOSC4CANCER](#) project and [CLARIN](#). These last two use FAIR material produced in the context of Skills4EOSC and the use of this should be monitored, as well as collect feedback from its exploitation.

The Communication team in WP8 will design and implement a series of training and communication materials branded for distribution to Skills4EOSC Competence Centres, data professionals in Open Science at universities, and research institutes across Europe. Specifically, this activity includes:

1. **Guidelines targeted towards project partners** to refine or draft deliverables for publication as manuals or guidelines. These guidelines aim to present outcomes in an operational and user-friendly manner, incorporating checklists and practical examples.
2. **A series of publications derived from Skills4EOSC deliverables**, available in digital downloadable and printable formats.
3. **A Toolkit for the Competence Centres** will be created, combining the materials developed for the aforementioned point 2 with additional ad-hoc digital resources. These will encompass leaflets, how-to guides, FAQ web pages, and slides designed to showcase the added value of the Skills4EOSC

Competence Centres Network. The aim is for these resources to be utilized and customized by the Competence Centres to broaden their national, regional, and thematic networks.